

Effect of wearing a bra on upper body skin temperature during exercise

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Introduction

Women wear bras to support breasts and the support also helps to reduce breast pain and movement during exercise [1]. Bras are usually tight-fit and of multi-layer that prevent heat and moisture transfer. Therefore, a sports bra can represent a physical advantage but a thermal disadvantage. Although the thermal response of the breasts to exercise has yet to be investigated, previous research has shown that clothing reduces convective and evaporative cooling [2]. In a recent study about the breast skin temperature underneath a sports bra by taking thermal images, it was found that the polyester sports bra demonstrated greater thermal comfort and enabled a greater change in skin temperature than the composite sports bra [3]. It was concluded that following short-duration exercise, sports bras reduced the cooling ability of the breast. Due to the limit of the thermal images only taken before and after the exercise, the effect that a sports bra has on skin temperature and thermal comfort during the exercise has yet to be investigated. The aim of this study was to investigate local skin temperature and thermoregulation during and after moderate exercise in mild environment.

Methods

Two bras were used, bra A has two thick cup pads while bra B doesn't have cup pads. A sports ensemble (long sleeve T-shirts and long pants) made of polyester were worn together with the bras respectively. A 34-segment Newton type sweating manikin (MTNW, Seattle, USA) with an additional bust part was used for the tests. The comfort test was carried out in a moderate environment ($T_a=21^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{RH}=50\%$, $V_a=0.4\text{m/s}$). A 40-min vigorous exercise (10 METs, manikin walking at 55 double steps per minute) followed by a 30-min rest (1.8 MET, manikin standing still) were simulated. The skin temperature, the body core temperature and the whole body sweat rate S_w over time were recorded every 30 seconds.

Table 1: Rct and Ret of two bras

Bras	Rct: entire ($^\circ\text{Cm}^2/\text{W}$)	Rct: breast ($^\circ\text{Cm}^2/\text{W}$)	Ret: entire ($\text{Pa.m}^2/\text{W}$)	Ret: breast ($\text{Pa.m}^2/\text{W}$)
Bra A	0.09	0.138	7.295	15.3
Bra B	0.088	0.116	7.24	13.812

Results and discussion

As shown in Table 1, although the local Rct and Ret at breast of Bra-A are higher than the respective ones of Bra-B, their contribution to the entire Rct and Ret of the manikin is small. Therefore, the mean skin temperature MST, core temperature T_{re} and the total sweat rate S_w didn't show big difference among three conditions. As shown in Fig. 1(a), S_w began to increase 6-min after exercise started, and reached same peak of 30g/min at a same time around 26-min after exercise started. Fig. 1(b) shows the local skin temperature (T_{sk}) at the breast (Br), and stomach (St) respectively. During the first 5-min, all T_{sk} dropped greatly due to the ventilation caused by walking. After sweating started at 6 min, T_{sk} varied among conditions. At breast, because of the higher Rct and Ret of Bra-A, T_{sk} didn't drop while T_{sk} of Bra-B and No-bra dropped along with the increasing of S_w . After S_w reached the maximum, the bra and the above T-shirt part got totally wet and the evaporating rate also reached a peak. When evaporative heat loss didn't increase anymore, all T_{sk} increased. T_{sk} turned to decline after the exercise stopped. At stomach, during the period of S_w increasing, all T_{sk} only dropped for a few minutes, then kept constant, and began to increase earlier than T_{sk} at breast did. During the period of maximum S_w , all T_{sk} increased greatly at a similar rate. The sharp increase of T_{sk} indicated moisture condensation at stomach. The T_{sk} increase of No-

bra was obviously smaller than those of two bras, indicating that more moisture condensed at stomach when the breast was covered by a bra.

Figure 1 Comfort test result

Conclusions

Through the comfort test with a female sweating manikin, it was found that the cooling at the breast was delayed because of the bra layer, especially when the bra was with thick cup pads. It was also found that moisture went down and condensed at stomach, especially when the vapor diffusion was blocked at breast by an additional bra layer. However, real human wear trial needs to be carried out to confirm the findings in future.

References

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